

Examining the Causes and Effects of Project Change Orders on Government's Construction Projects: Insights from the Perspectives of Construction Professionals in Ghana

Christopher Dick-Sagoe

Department of Development Studies, University of South Africa, South Africa

Project change orders increase the duration, cost and quality of projects, usually leading to disputes among project stakeholders. In this study, the major causes of project change orders and their influence on project performance (by comparing actual time, cost and quality to the initially agreed project estimates. It further assesses the views of construction project professionals on the effects that project change orders have on government's project. With the use of quantitative methods and a sample of 180 respondents, the study identified the major causes of project change orders to scope and changes to plan, changes to specification, omission of designs, errors and defective workmanship. Additional causes of project change orders were defective workmanship, lack of judgement and experience of the consultants, insufficient project objectives, insufficient working drawings, lack of adequate coordination among the experts and specification changes. Measures employed to reduce the occurrence of change orders were proper supervision of works on site, making sure that specifications are within budget, making sure that site investigations are done properly, adequate and intensive communication among the parties, recruiting competent staff to handle the engineering and design section, and coordinated and proper planning among the parties. Finally, the effects of change orders were identified as an increase in overhead expenses, delayed payment, project cost increases, delay in project completion schedule, and demolition and rework. The recommendations raised include the intensification of coordination and communication among the project professionals. In addition, well-scrutinized recruitment of project professionals was also recommended.

Keywords: Public projects, project variation, project change orders, project management

Studies from researchers like Chalchissa (2021), Oyedele et al. (2003), and Jayawardena, Ramachandra and Rotimi (2014) reveals how change orders affect the performance (success) governments construction projects. This statement means that for government construction projects to be effective, project change orders must be avoided at all costs, as it negatively affects projects' quality, budgeted cost and initial (estimated) project time (Varghese et al., 2018; Nyangwara & Datche, 2015; Soares, 2012). By virtue of the involvement of different stakeholders in their execution, local government construction projects continue to face change orders (Koushki et al., 2005).

The acceptance of change leads to the issuance of change orders, which document the scope of the change and the likely impact the change will have on the budgeted cost and time (performance) of the project (Jayawardena, Ramachandra, & Rotimi, 2014). Alternatively, unagreed changes by the stakeholders of the project result in disputes (Lokhande & Ahmed, 2015). In this instance, the execution of the project is significantly affected and reduces the chances of successful completion of the project. In addition, project

change orders lead to additional supply of equipment, which has cost increase implications (Assbeihat & Sweis, 2015). In support of this statement, project change orders lead to project delays and consequently, abandonment, a phenomenon which likely leads to disputes among project stakeholders (Aibinu & Jagboro, 2002). These narrations explain the strong connection between project performance (measured in time, cost, & quality) and change orders (Pheng & Chuan, 2006; & Chalchissa, 2021).

Change order, which is the focus of this study, is defined as additional or deleted work from the initial scope of work agreed by all stakeholders (Zawawi et al., 2010). This change alters the estimated project time and contract amount agreed by all stakeholders, including the project's quality. Change orders take the form of replacement, addition or deletion of the initial project scope agreed by all stakeholders (Ndihokubwayo & Haupt, 2009). From these explanations present project change orders as paying for the mistakes of other stakeholders by project owners and as a disruption of project time and workflow to the project contractors. In these situations, project change tarnishes the cordial relationship among the various stakeholders. On the positive side, project change orders improve project outcomes for all project stakeholders. Change orders also tie up resources, which can be used for other important projects. Researchers like Hegazy, Zanaty, and Crierson (2001) attributes the causes of project change orders to subsurface conditions different from the initial contract as indicated on the contract documents, unavailability of equipment and materials, change of project scope initiated by the owners and/or designers during the execution, value engineering proposal, change in the regulatory legislations after the award of the contract and design errors omission and correction.

Author Note

Christopher Dick-Sagoe, Department of Development Studies
University of South Africa, South Africa

Email: dicksagoe@gmail.com

I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Christopher Dick-Sagoe, Department of Development Studies
University of South Africa, South Africa

Email: dicksagoe@gmail.com

Empirically, several works like Ndiokubwayo and Haupt (2009), Akomah, Mustapha, Mensah, and Lawson (2023), and Ijaola and Iyagba (2012) have been conducted on project change orders. An example of these works is Ijaola and Iyagba (2012) who compared change orders in construction projects in Oman and Nigeria. The authors were interested in identifying the causes, effects, benefits and remedies of change orders in these countries. In addition, their study was meant to compare the scenario of change orders in both countries and to determine areas for policy improvement. Recently, authors like Akomah, Mustapha, Mensah, and Lawson (2023) have contributed to the change orders in the construction industry in Ghana. The authors identified the causes of project change orders on public construction projects from 2000 to 2014 using document analysis in Ghana's Central Region and realised that 348 projects were executed during the period, of which 84 faced change orders. The change orders were additional work and substitutions and because of this, the cost and time of projects with multiple change orders were higher than a single change order.

In response to these narrations, this study was embarked upon to unearth the causes, effects and remedies for project change orders from construction professionals (project owners, contractors, suppliers & consultants) in Ghana. The study carefully included construction professionals with more than five years of experience dealing with government construction projects in Ghana. Five years of working experience was considered for reasons of the rapid changes in technology and the continuous changes in government policies on public projects. Further five years ceiling allowed the inclusion of contemporary information that is relevant to policy making process. Identifying, through analysis, the causes and effects of change orders on public projects is necessary for managing public projects as these changes adversely impact project performance (initially agreed time, budgeted cost & quality).

Public infrastructure in developing countries consistently face waste and inefficiencies, as one-third of all public projects in Ghana are abandoned and 20 percent of governments funds are spent on abandoned public infrastructure projects in Ghana (Williams, 2017). However, the reason remains a mirage as there is generally no hard evidence about the causes of public infrastructure project failure. Based on these justifications, this study has been embarked on addressing the following research question. These are:

- What causes public project change orders in Ghana?
- How do the causes of public change order predict the performance of public projects in Ghana?

The Concept of Project Change Orders

Frequently, public projects face change orders on a daily basis (Thomas & Napolitan, 1995; & Ming, Martin, & Chimay, 2004). Some of these project changes can be considered as predicted changes, which are expected to occur and planned ahead of time, whereas others can be considered as developing changes. Developing changes, in the sense that they occur unexpectedly, making it difficult to anticipate. For such changes to the project to be official, the stakeholder proposing the change must initiate the changes in written or oral form (Ssegawa et al., 2002), stating the reasons for the change, which could be internal or external (Ming et al., 2004). External factors accounting for project change orders

include economic fluctuations, changes in government, changes in clients' taste and mechanical modifications. Internal factors also include management changes, long-term survival system changes of the organisation and changes in authoritative locations. Disagreement in contract document, delays in decision making due to obstacles, contractual workers' desired productivity, changes and extensions from clients, financial difficulties and poor project objectives were identified by Sunday (2010) as the causal factors for project change orders. Arain and Pheng (2006) refined these factors by categorising them into four: consultant, client and other associated changes are included.

Measuring Project Performance and Success

Project success and performance are used interchangeably, and are measured on three critical success factors, which include public infrastructure projects meeting the required quality, public infrastructure projects completed within the budgeted cost, and within the budgeted time (Chalchissa, 2021). These three criteria are often referred to as the iron triangle.

Causes of Project Change Orders

Public projects inevitably undergo changes, which are typically caused by the involvement of many stakeholders in the project's implementation. Kaming et al. (1997) found that design modifications were the primary cause of schedule overruns in 31 Indonesian high-rise projects. The role of project stakeholders (contractors, consultants, or clients) and the nature of public projects were used by Chan and Kumaraswamy (1997) to classify the causes and determine the relative importance of the elements causing project delays in Hong Kong's construction projects. Poor site management and supervision, unexpected ground conditions, delayed decision-making by all project stakeholders, client-initiated adjustments, and required work modifications were the factors that were found. Similar to this, Goudreau (2001) noted that inadequate contractor experience, poor planning, financing, and payments, owner interference, labour productivity, and slow decision-making were the main causes of the project delays in construction projects, while Al-Momani (2000) identified user changes as the primary cause of project delays in 130 public projects in Jordan. Kezar and Holcombe (2021) established two major categories (non-excusable and excusable delays) to outline the reasons for project delays. Excusable delays are brought on by client or consultant, while non-excusable delays are related to the project contractor.

Alarryan et al. (2014) used a questionnaire to gather data from 385 respondents (owners, Contractors, & consultants) in order to investigate the reasons behind project change orders on both private and public projects in Kuwait. Owners alter plans based on their research, which results in project modifications and raises the project modifications and raises the projects originally agreed-upon cost. On the other hand, Ahmed et al. (2018) found the common elements that affect cost rises in the building sector of Pakistan. Their study, which used questionnaire surveys for clients, consultants, and builders shows that top three variables contributing to cost escalation in the construction business were inflation, delayed payments, and financial difficulties. Moreover, Ahmed et al. (2018) noted that the difficulties public projects encounter include contract agreements, work schedules, change orders, and payments.

Empirical Reviews on Project Variation Orders

Homaid, Eldosouky, and Al-Ghamdi (2011) looked into the 21 causes and 11 potential outcomes of change orders. In addition, nine practices were reported to management, including change order management. The analysis revealed eleven significant causes and seven major outcomes. The consultant is also revealed to be the most accountable party for the change orders. Change orders caused an average 11.3% increase in the total cost of the construction projects. According to the research, the most common cause of change orders in those projects is owner requirements, and the most typical outcome of change orders is cost overruns.

Owner-made changes to plans are the most common source of modification orders, according to Aljeshi and Almarzouq (2008), Aldubaisi (2000), and Zawawi (2010). Changes in thinking, materials, and processes are the second most prevalent source of change orders, followed by design faults and omissions. The two main effects of change orders were found to be an increase in project cost and length. Another study discovered that the best technique for managing change orders is to reach a mutually acceptable agreement between the parties. The level of integration between design and construction services was linked to the initiation of change orders in a construction project (Soares, 2012).

Keane, Sertyesilisik, and Ross (2010) used a questionnaire survey to identify the sources and implications of variance in construction projects, as well as make recommendations for how variation might be avoided or minimized in the future. Jawad, Abdulkader, and Ali (2009) studied variation orders in big building construction, including their sources, impacts, and controls. The investigation concluded that the owner is the principal cause of the variance, with civil and structural accounting for the vast bulk of it. Wu, Hsieh, and Cheng (2005) performed a statistical analysis of reasons for design changes in Taiwanese highway construction.

Olsen et al. (2012) investigated the most common sources of change orders in order to determine which work divisions are more vulnerable to change orders. According to the findings, the majority of the revisions were the result of design defects. Bassioni and Hamza (2005) investigated the key drivers of change orders in Kuwaiti building development. According to the report, owners account for 47% of modification orders, architects and engineers for 26%, and contractors for 12%. The investigation discovered that design changes accounted for 38% of the reasons, design flaws and errors accounted for 24%, on-site challenges accounted for 12%, and regulatory agency adjustments accounted for 12%.

Wambek (2011) investigated the similarities and differences in starting time and task duration variance across craftsmen, foremen, and project managers. He identified the causes of variance, which account for more than 19 hours of fluctuation per week. Alnuaimi et al. (2010) observed discrepancies in public construction projects in Oman. Arain and Pheng (2005) investigated the influence of variations in construction projects in depth. Oladapo (2007) studies the role of variance in cost and time overruns. According to the survey, the most prevalent sources of variation are specification and scope modifications, which are mostly driven by project owners and consultants. Osman (2009) conducted an extensive analysis of the potential consequences of variation orders in Malaysian construction projects. According to the report, the five most significant effects of deviations are increased project cost, additional contractor payment, increased overhead expenses, a delay in

completion schedule, rework, and demolition.

According to the report, the most common causes of variation are changes in specification and scope, which are typically pushed by project managers and consultants. Osman (2009) conducted a thorough investigation into the potential consequences of variation orders in Malaysian building projects. According to the report, the five most significant consequences of deviations are increased project cost, additional contractor payment, increased overhead expenses, a delay in completion schedule, rework, and demolition. The survey's purpose is to learn more about those individuals' personal experiences with change orders so that causes, effects, and control measures may be discovered. The next sections discuss the questionnaire's contents and scoring methodology, followed by data analysis to identify the most common causes, consequences, and controls for project change orders.

Gyadu-Asiedu (2009) doctoral study examines how construction project performance is assessed in Ghana's construction industry, with particular emphasis on the differing perspectives of construction practitioners (such as contractors & consultants) and clients. The research recognises that traditional performance evaluation in construction often focuses mainly on the "iron triangle" of cost, time, and quality, which may not fully capture the broader dimensions of project success. Using a quantitative survey approach, the study collected data from key stakeholders in Ghana's construction sector, including contractors, consultants, and project clients. The research employed statistical modelling techniques to analyse the factors influencing project performance and to develop a model that integrates the perspectives of both practitioners and clients.

The findings reveal that construction project performance in Ghana is influenced by several factors, including project management practices, stakeholder communication, financial management, and contractor competence. The study also highlights that clients and practitioners often evaluate project success differently, with clients placing more emphasis on value delivery and satisfaction, while practitioners tend to focus on technical and operational performance indicators.

Ijaola and Iyagba (2012) investigated the causes, consequences, benefits, and remedies of modification orders in construction projects in Nigeria and Oman. This was done to evaluate project change order situations in both countries and find potential areas for improvement. Ndiokubwayo and Haupt (2009) investigated changes in labour productivity. Aside from these authors, several others have studied the causes and effects of variation orders, including Hanif, Khurshid, Malik, and Nauman (2014), in Pakistan, Fetene (2008), Tadesse (2009), and Tewodros (2015) in Ethiopia. However, studies such as Chalchissa (2021) consider variation orders by correlating variation orders to project performance. As a result, it is reasonable to conclude that little is known about the impact of variances on public project performance. This is exacerbated by the lack of a similar study in Ghana.

In assessing the causes and impacts of change orders on construction projects in Nigeria, Oladiran et al. (2018) acknowledge the complexity of construction projects, which makes variation orders unavoidable. Their study concluded that the ability to identify the causes of variation orders will make it easier for researchers and practitioners to identify changes and develop strategies to avoid variation orders in projects, particularly to reduce the negative impacts such variation orders have on government construction

projects. They were driven to discover the causes and effects, as well as crucial strategies to limit the recurrence of such variation orders on Nigerian government construction projects. In addition, they were motivated to determine the frequency of such project change orders. They used a convenience sampling technique for their investigation. Their study used questionnaires to collect data from 50 respondents, all of whom were building construction professionals in Nigeria's Lagos state. However, only 45 of the 50 questionnaires issued to professionals were returned. Therefore, the final number of respondents used for the study is 45. Their research identifies the following as the leading reasons for project variation orders. These include changes to the scope and plan of work, among others. However, including all parties engaged in a project was deemed the greatest approach for controlling change orders on government building projects in Lagos, Nigeria. It was discovered that cost overrun was the consequence of project change order on Lagos government's construction project. Thus, the authors' advice includes that the government's building projects do not overlook the need for regular participation from all parties involved in the project.

Method

Participants

The total population used in the study is 298. This list includes all registered and current members of Ghana's Association of Building Construction and Civil Engineering Professionals. A sample of 180 was drawn from this population using Krejcie and Morgan's (1980) table, with a 5% error margin.

Research Design

This study used the quantitative survey design. Surveys are a well-organized activity that allows us to gather information directly from

individuals. Surveys, as a quantitative method of data collection, allow researchers to gather information from a large sample of the population (Kothari, 2004).

Data Collection and Analysis

Questionnaires were employed to get information from respondents. The questionnaire items were closed-ended questions that supplied data to answer the specific research questions posed for this study. The questionnaires include the following questions. The first sections document the respondents' personal information, while the remaining questions collect information on the causes of project variation, measures of importance in project management, the effects of project variation on local government projects, and the frequency with which project variation occurs on local government projects. For easy assessment and measurement, a scale was employed. Five- and three-point Likert scale tool was employed for respondents to rate their agreement from 1 to 5, where, for example 1 = very low agreement, 2 = low agreement, 3 = moderate agreement, 4 = high agreement and 5 = very high agreement. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistical methods (means). An ethical clearance was provided by the ethical committee of the Ghana Communication Technology University, Accra, Ghana.

Results and Discussion

Causes of Change Variations on Government Construction Projects in Ghana

Government construction projects are critical for any economy since they propel it forward; consequently, government-led initiatives are referred to as development projects. This subsection explores the causes of modification orders in government development construction projects.

Table 1
Causes of Project Change Orders

Causes of project change orders	Disagreement (%)	Neutral (%)	Agreement (%)
Scope and plan changes	3	28	69
Specifications related changes	7	31	62
Design Omissions and Errors	10	28	62
Defective in workmanship	10	28	62
Lack of adequate co-ordination	14	24	62
Schedule changes	7	34	59
Change in regulations of the government	10	31	59
Change in technology	3	38	59
Unexpected conditions	3	41	55
Impediments in prompt decision making	10	34	55
Design Change by the consultant	3	45	52
Change in the economic conditions	3	45	52
Consultant's lack of experience	21	28	52
Complexity in project design	10	38	52
Contractor not involved in the design stage	17	31	52
Lack of adequate project objectives	21	34	45
Lack of adequate working drawings	28	31	41
Weather conditions	17	45	38
Consultant's unaware of available materials	28	34	38
Conflicts in contract documents	14	52	34

Note. Source: Author's construct, 2026

From Table 1, the respondents attributed the causes of change orders in construction projects to several factors. All the respondents considered 15 factors to contribute to project change orders. These 15 factors were the ones that were affirmed (that is, rated agree, & strongly agree) by the respondents as the causes of project change orders. Eight (8) of the 15 factors were considered as the major causes of project change orders. This means that their scores were far above 50 percent (in this case ranges from 69% to 59%), whereas 7 factors, which were also considered as the other causes of project change orders in this study, had scores between 52 percent and 55 percent, were considered as just the causes of project change orders.

From these categories, the 8 major causes of project change orders identified by the respondents were scope and plan changes (69%), specification changes (62%), design omissions and errors (62%), defective workmanship (62%) and lack of adequate coordination among the project stakeholders (62%). The rest are schedule changes (59%), changes in the regulations of the government (59%) and changes in technology (59%). This then takes us to the analysis of the other factors contributing to project change order. The next paragraph presents the other causal factors of project change in Ghana.

The 7 factors, considered in this study by virtue of the score attached by the respondents as the other causes of project change orders were outlined, in order of importance, as unexpected conditions (55%), impediment to prompt decision making (55%), design changes by the consultant (52%), changes in economic conditions (52%), lack of experience on the side of the consultant (52%), complexity in the project design (52%) and contractors not involved in the design stage of the project (52%).

Possible cause of project change orders include lack of adequate project objectives, lack of adequate working drawings, weather conditions, unaware of adequate available materials and conflict between contract documents received less support (meaning got less than 50% support from the respondents), thus were not considered as part of the causes of project change order on government's construction projects in Ghana.

To discuss this result, we realized that the major causes of project change orders, the top five causes identified in Table 1, include scope and plan changes, and specification-related changes. The revelation from these changes reveals that government projects are arguably handled by experts who operate as silos, each stakeholder seeing themselves as not part of the other. However, the nature of their work is such that one person's inputs become another person's output. The meaning and implications derived from these two main causes and supported (or made evident) with the last five causes of project change order (lack of adequate coordination) portrays lack of adequate consultations, coordination and communication among the various stakeholders. Again, the third and the fourth main causes of project change order, design omissions and errors and defective workmanship simply and arguably portrays an issue of poor recruitment system or better still, favouritism in the recruitment of experts (stakeholders) in the allocation of projects, thus clouding the use of proper assessment methods for selecting experienced experts (stockholders), such as independent, blind and scientific selection of experts, in the award of contract for such projects to experts who deserve such offers based on practical work experience.

These results from this study were further compared with similar studies of other authors, such as Alaryan et al. (2014) attributes the

causes of change orders in construction projects in Kuwait to the change of plan and change of project scope. The rest are problems on site, errors and omissions in design and change of schedule. These findings corroborate those found in this study, as this study identified common factors like a change of scope and errors in design.

Furthermore, Oladiran, Umeadi, and Onatayo (2018) conducted a similar study in Nigeria that is considered close to this study because they share a common economic block, West Africa, identified the following as the causes of project change orders in Lagos, Nigeria. These are adjustments to the scope, specifications, and design made by the consultant. They also highlighted timeline changes, poor project objectives, and design mistakes and omissions. These conclusions are consistent with the findings of this study, which identified scope and plan alterations, specification-related adjustments, design omissions and errors, substandard workmanship, and a lack of effective coordination. These revelations led the study to dig further to find the level of occurrence of change orders in the government's construction projects in Ghana (Table 2). The level of occurrence of change orders on local government construction projects was considered good to help shed more light on understanding the causes of change orders.

Level of Occurrence of Change Orders in Government Construction Projects

The occurrence of project change orders were like that of the causes. According to the respondents, the frequent causes of modification orders on government construction projects include substandard workmanship, consultant lack of judgement and experience, inadequate project objectives, and inadequate working drawings. These characteristics are like the elements that contribute to project change orders. These enumerated occurrence factors also highlight issues with the recruitment of experts with little or no experience, leaving them vulnerable to mistakes such as defective workmanship, a lack of adequate experience and judgement, and inadequate project objectives that the experts are supposed to develop.

Another issue identified as contributing to project change orders was lack of collaboration among project professionals (experts). A quick examination of the causes and frequency of occurrence highlights the importance of ensuring that appropriate, qualified professionals are brought on board to manage government projects. For example, the incidence of substandard craftsmanship, the consultant's lack of judgement and expertise, inadequate project objectives, and inadequate work drawings all point to the same thing: inexperience among the professionals. This study was no exception to this revelation.

Further, the analysis on the level of occurrence of change orders made it clear that factors such as change in specification (52%) and lack of coordination (52%) sometimes contribute to the level of occurrence of change orders. Analytically, these two points point to the presence of inexperienced experts and lack of coordination and communication among the various experts, as already pointed out in this study.

This study identifies other factors likely to occur frequently in government projects and presents them in Table 2. Integration and intensified collaboration, coordination, effective communication and constant meeting and interaction among the experts remain key to reducing the occurrences identified in this study. To discuss the findings on the level of occurrence of change orders, the work of

Table 2*Level of Occurrence of Change Orders in Government Projects*

Level of occurrence of change orders	Never (%)	Sometimes (%)	Often (%)
Defective workmanship	14	28	59
Consultant lacks judgement and experience	14	31	55
Inadequate working drawing	10	38	52
Inadequate project objectives	10	38	52
Lack of consultant's knowledge of available materials	21	31	48
Weather conditions	21	31	48
Change in design by the consultant	14	38	48
Conflicts between contract documents	14	41	45
Change of schedule	14	41	45
Design complexity	17	38	45
Lack of contractor's involvement in design	24	31	45
Technology change	14	45	41
Change in government regulations	10	48	41
Impediment in prompt decision making	21	38	41
Unforeseen conditions	14	45	41
Change in specifications	10	52	38
Errors and omissions in design	21	41	38
Change in economic conditions	21	41	38
Change of plan or scope	24	41	34
Lack of co-ordination	14	52	34

Note. Source: Author's field construct, 2026

Oladiran et al. (2018) was considered. Oladiran et al. (2018) observe the level of occurrence of change order, in order of importance, as follows. These are changes in design by the consultant and changes in specifications. The rest, according to them, are unforeseen conditions and defective workmanship. This corroborates the findings of this study as common factors such as defective workmanship and change in specifications were observed to be common among the levels of occurrence between the two different

studies.

Measures for Controlling the Occurrence of Project Change Orders

Arranged logically from the highest to the lowest, the professionals outlined the measures for reducing the rate of occurrence of change order in government's construction projects in Ghana (see Table 3).

Table 3*Measures to Reduce the Occurrence of Project Change Orders*

Measures	Not	Less	Important	Very
	Important	Important		Important
Proper supervision of works	0	3	7	90
Specification within budget	0	0	10	90
Site investigations should be done properly	0	0	10	90
Intensive Communication among parties	0	0	14	86
Competent professionals in the design and engineering section	3	0	10	86
Proper and coordinated planning among parties involved	3	3	7	86
Proper Forecast of unforeseen conditions	0	3	14	83
Proper and Adequate co-ordination at design stage	0	3	14	83
Consultant contract documents	0	0	17	83
Briefing the project Client	0	3	17	79
Adequate information on materials and procurement procedure plans	0	0	24	76
Completed drawings at the tender stage	0	0	41	59

Note. Source: Author's field construct, 2026

From Table 3 the highest to lowest, the most critical measures to reduce the occurrence of project change orders, according to the professionals include proper work supervision, specification within

budget, proper site investigations, intensive communication among parties, competent design and engineering staff, proper and coordinated planning among parties involved, proper forecast of

unforeseen conditions, proper and adequate co-ordination at the design stage, consultant contract documents, and adequate information on materials and procurement procedure plans.

These measures were like those offered by Gokulkarthi and Gowrishankar (2015) in India, Oladiran, Umeadi, and Onatayo (2018) in Nigeria and Oladiran et al. (2018) in Kuwait. In Kuwait, the measures to control change orders according to Oladiran et al. (2018) are consistent checking and reviewing of contract documents, reviewing project design before change is approved and justification of project change. They further state the rest to include making clear the scope of project change orders, and lastly, all project change orders are properly stated in writing and approved by the relevant office.

In India, Gokulkarthi and Gowrishankar (2015) describe strategies to mitigate the impact of change orders, such as clearly outlining the scope of work after a change order has been imposed, putting change orders in writing, and negotiating with experienced and knowledgeable personnel. The remainder, according to them, analyze the change orders to see if they are practical before approval is granted, and then construction parties interact and discuss such change orders. Intensive communication among the parties involved in the change order, as well as professional engagements in the change orders, were prevalent themes in this study and the examined studies.

Effects of Project Change Orders

Change orders in government construction projects come with a cost

(effects). These effects are shown in Table 4. The impacts are numerous and include the following, as identified by project professionals (from highest to lowest). These include increased overhead charges, payment delays, project cost increases, delays in completion schedules, and rework and destruction. The remaining effects include slowed building progress, lower productivity, lower quality, procurement delays, and increased contractor payments.

The implications of project change highlighted in this study include some expected time delays as well as an estimated cost increase for government building projects in Ghana. A secondary study conducted by Gokulkarthi and Gowrishankar (2015) discovered that project delays reduce productivity, cause additional delays in scheduled (budgeted) project completion time and cost, lead to conflict between project contractor and project owner, and result in poor work output. They also claim that project change orders result in additional payments to the contractor and delays in the delivery of project resources such as tools and supplies. Thus, a basic examination reveals that change orders raise project costs, delay the project's expected completion time, lengthen the duration of project individual operations, and cause payment delays.

These factors identified by Gokulkarthi and Gowrishankar (2015) as the effects of project change orders and discussed in this section are like those identified in this study and reported in Table 4, which include increase in project cost, delays in project completion time, delays in the supply of project materials and tools (resources) as a result of delays in procurement and productivity degradation, just to mention few.

Table 4
Effects of Change Orders on Government Construction Projects

Effects of change orders	No effect	Low effect	Medium effect	High effect
Increase in overhead expenses	0	3	14	83
Delay in payment	0	0	17	83
Increase in project cost	3	7	10	79
Delay in completion schedule	0	3	17	79
Rework and demolition	0	0	21	79
Construction progress is affected	0	0	21	79
Productivity degradation	0	3	24	72
Quality degradation	0	0	28	72
Procurement delay	3	0	28	69
Additional payment for contractor	0	7	28	66
Disputes among professionals	0	7	28	66
Poor professional relations	0	6	32	62

Note. Source: Author's field construct, 2026

Conclusion

Governments around the world take on development projects (mostly construction projects) to help their individual countries develop and alleviate poverty. In this regard, the government will continue to invest in construction projects to improve the lives of its residents.

This study provides insights into the dynamics of change implementation in Ghanaian government initiatives. It solicited feedback from a sample of project experts working on a variety of public projects to better understand the impact of change on their projects. This study investigated the origins, impacts, and methods taken to mitigate the impact of modification orders on government

projects in Ghana. With the topic as its focus, the study sought to determine the causes of project change orders, the frequency of project change orders, measures taken to mitigate the effects of project change orders on government construction projects in Ghana, and finally, the effects of project change orders on government construction projects in Ghana.

This study recorded and presented a thorough analysis of the factors that contribute to the causes and effects, as well as a deep dive into problems pertinent to policymaking, addressing government construction projects in Ghana. For example, the report emphasizes the importance of governments ensuring that projects are given to experienced experts capable of delivering expert work and anticipating or predicting specific environmental circumstances that

may necessitate project modification orders. Again, government building projects should require regular contact, meetings, coordination, and improved communication among all project stakeholders (professionals). These methods, when implemented, will go a long way toward reducing or providing better strategies to manage project change orders, which provide challenges and danger to all project stakeholders.

Policy Recommendations

All government project experts should be involved in performance contracting. This means that specialists will be compensated depending on meeting pre-agreed-upon targets. This contract agreement signed by the government and several specialists would keep the experts on their toes, requiring them to continually focus on performance and avoid anything that would reduce their performance. This technique aims to decrease design flaws and omissions, increase coordination, and repair poor workmanship.

The contract document signed between the government (owner) and the project experts should leave enough room for intensive and ongoing interaction among the various experts, in the form of regular debriefing and coordination, during which the various experts will discuss work progress in those meetings. This will prevent any unexpected and frequent modifications to the project's scope, plan, and specs. At the very least, an intensive and detailed discussion will anticipate the potential of such changes occurring, and preparations will be developed to deal with them.

References

- Ahmed, S., Memon, A. H., Memon, N. A., Laghari, A. N., Akhund, M. A., & Imad, H. U. (2018). Common factors of cost escalation in construction industry of Pakistan. *Engineering, Technology and Applied Science Research*, 8(6), 3508-3511.
- Aibinu, A. A., & Jagboro, G. O. (2002). The effects of construction delays on project delivery in Nigerian construction industry. *International Journal of Project Management*, 20(8), 593-599.
- Akomah, B. B., Mustapha, Z., Mensah, J. W., & Lawson, R. W. (2023). Variations in building construction projects in Ghana: A public organisational perspective. *Baltic Journal of Real Estate Economics and Construction Management*, 11(1), 221-239.
- Alaryan, A., Emadbeltagi, A. E., & Dawood, M. (2014). Causes and effects of change orders on construction projects in Kuwait. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, 4(7), 1-8.
- Al-Momani, A. H. (2000). Construction delay: A quantitative analysis. *International Journal of Project Management*, 18(1), 51-59.
- Alnuaimi, A. S., Taha, R. A., Al Mohsin, M., & Al-Harhi, A. S. (2010). Causes, effects, benefits, and remedies of change orders on public construction projects in Oman. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 136(5), 615-622.
- Anderson, A. A. (2006). *The community builder's approach to theory of change*. A practical guide to theory development. The Aspen Institute Roundtable on Community Change. Url: http://www.dochas.ie/Shared/Files/4/TOC_fac_guide.pdf.
- Arain, F. M., & Pheng, L. S. (2005). How design consultants perceive potential causes of variation orders for institutional buildings in Singapore. *Architectural Engineering and Design Management*, 1(3), 181-196.
- Assibey-Mensah, G. O. (2009). Ghana's construction industry and global competition: A research note. *Journal of Black Studies*, 39(6), 974-989.
- Bassioni, H., & Hamza, N. (2005). *Sources of change orders in Kuwait building construction* (Doctoral dissertation, MSC thesis, Department of Construction and Building Engineering, Arab Academy for Science, Technology and Maritime Transport, Alexandria, Egypt).
- Beatham, S., Anumba, C., Thorpe, T., & Hedges, I. (2004). KPIs: A critical appraisal of their use in construction. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 11(1), 93-117.
- Bhagavan, M. R., & Virgin, I. (2004). *Generic aspects of institutional capacity development in developing countries*. Stockholm: Stockholm Environment Institute.
- Bromiley, P., McShane, M., Nair, A., & Rustambekov, E. (2015). Enterprise risk management: Review, critique, and research directions. *Long Range Planning*, 48(4), 265-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2014.07.005>
- Bromiley, P., McShane, M., Nair, A., & Rustambekov, E. (2015). Enterprise risk management: Review, critique, and research directions. *Long Range Planning*, 48(4), 265-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2014.07.005>
- Chan, D. W., & Kumaraswamy, M. M. (1997). A comparative study of causes of time overruns in Hong Kong construction projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 15(1), 55-63.
- Chaplowe, S. G. (2008). *Monitoring and evaluation planning*. American Red Cross/CRS M&E Module Series, American Red Cross and Catholic Relief Services (CRS), Washington, DC and Baltimore, MD.
- Coryn, C. L., Noakes, L. A., Westine, C. D., & Schröter, D. C. (2011). A systematic review of theory-driven evaluation practice from 1990 to 2009. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 32(2), 199-226.
- Cummings, T. G., & Worley, C. G. (2009). *Organization development and change*. Cengage learning.
- Diallo, A., & Thuillier, D. (2005). The success of international development projects, trust and communication: An African perspective. *International Journal of Project Management*, 23(3), 237-252.
- Gokulkarthi, M., & Gowrishankar, K. S. (2015). A study on impacts of change order in construction projects. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Research*, 3(4), 3221-5687.
- Goudreau, H. (2001). *The five key elements of a construction contract: Forget them and you are in trouble*. HG & Associates. <http://www.hgassociates.com/articlecontracts.html>
- Gyadu-Asiedu, W. (2009). *Assessing construction project performance in Ghana: Modelling practitioners' and clients' perspectives* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Wolverhampton.
- Hegazy, T., Zaneldin, E., & Grierson, D. (2001). Improving design coordination for building projects. I: Information model. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 127(4), 322-329.
- Homaid, N. T. I., Eldosouky, A. I., & Al-Ghamdi, M. A. (2011). Change orders in Saudi linear construction projects. *Emirates Journal for Engineering Research*, 16(1), 33-42.
- Ijaola, I. A., & Iyagba, R. O. (2012). A comparative study of causes of change orders in public construction project in Nigeria and Oman. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(5), 495-501.
- Jawad, R. S. M., Abdulkader, M. R., & Ali, A. A. A. (2009). Variation orders in construction projects. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 170-176. <https://makhillpublications.co/public/index.php/view-article/1816-949x/jeasci.2009.170.176>
- Kaming, P. F., Olomolaiye, P. O., Holt, G. D., & Harris, F. C. (1997). Factors influencing construction time and cost overruns on high-rise projects in Indonesia. *Construction Management and Economics*, 15(1), 83-94.
- Keane, P. J., Sertysilisik, B., & Ross, A. D. (2010). Variations in construction projects: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction*, 15(2), 176-190. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13664381011063443>
- Kezar, A. J., & Holcombe, E. M. (2021). Leveraging multiple theories of change to promote reform: An examination of the AAU STEM initiative. *Educational Policy*, 35(6), 985-1013. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904819843594>
- Lokhande, M. A., & Ahmed, F. S. Y. (2015). Assessing consequences of change request impact in construction industry of Yemen: An explorative Likert-scale based survey design. *Management*, 5(5), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.mm.20150505.01>
- McIntyre, L. (1999). The practical skeptic: Core concepts in sociology. Mountain view. CA: Mayfield Publishing International, 311(6997), 109-112.
- Milimu, C. K. (2016). *The influences of change management practices on performance of Pinnacle Projects Ltd, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Ming, S., Martin, S., & Chimay, A. (2004). *Managing changes in construction projects*. Industrial Report, University of the West of England, Bristol, 7-10.
- Oladapo, A. A. (2007). A quantitative assessment of the cost and time impact of variation orders on construction projects. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 5(1), 35-48.
- Oladiran, O. J., Umeadi, C. N., & Onatayo, D. A. (2018). Evaluating change orders and their impacts on construction project performance in Lagos, Nigeria. *FUTY Journal of the Environment*, 12(2), 81-89.
- Olsen, D., Killingsworth, R., & Page, B. (2012, April). *Change order causation: Who is the guilty party?* 48th ASC annual international conference proceedings (Vol. 1, pp. 1-9).
- Osman, Z., Omran, A., & Foo, C. K. (2009). The potential effects of variation orders in construction projects. *Journal of Engineering*, 2, 141-152.
- Pinsonneault, A., & Kraemer, K. (1993). Survey research methodology in management information systems: An assessment. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 10(2), 75-105.
- Rashid, I., Elmikawi, M., & Saleh, A. (2012). The impact of change orders on construction projects: sports facilities case study. *Journal of American Science*, 8(8), 628-631.

- Soares, R. (2012). Change orders ordeal: The output of project disintegration. *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*, 2(1), 65-69.
- Ssegawa, J. K., Mfolwe, K. M., Makuke, B., & Kutua, B. (2002, November). *Construction variations: a scourge or a necessity*. Proceedings of the First International Conference of CIB W107 (pp. 11-13).
- Sunday, O. A. (2010, September). *Impact of variation orders on public construction projects*. 26th Annual ARCOM Conference, Leeds, UK.
- The World Bank (2003). *Country procurement assessment report: Ghana*, Report No. 29055, Vol. 2, the World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Thomas, H. R., & Napolitan, C. L. (1995). Quantitative effects of construction changes on labor productivity. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 121(3), 290-296.
- Wan, Abdullah Zawawi, N. A., Nik Azman, N. F. I., & Shamsul Kamar, M. S. (2010). *Sustainable construction practice: A review of Change Orders (CO) in Construction Projects*.
- Williams, M. J. (2017). The political economy of unfinished development projects: Corruption, clientelism, or collective choice? *American Political Science Review*, 111(4), 705-723.
- Wu, C. H., Hsieh, T. Y., & Cheng, W. L. (2005). Statistical analysis of causes for design change in highway construction in Taiwan. *International Journal of Project Management*, 23(7), 554-563.

Received February 26, 2026

Revision received March 8, 2026

Accepted March 13, 2026